

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF AI APPLICATION IN MONITORING AND ACCIDENT PREVENTION SYSTEMS AT INDUSTRIAL FACILITIES

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Abstract

The article examines the application of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies for monitoring and accident prevention at industrial facilities. The use of machine learning (ML) methods and computer vision (CV) for detecting hidden anomalies and predicting potential malfunctions is analyzed. The advantages of AI integration for enhancing the safety, reliability, and efficiency of industrial processes are studied. Using examples from companies such as Boeing, ExxonMobil, and Dow Inc., the importance of predictive analytics, which enables real-time data processing for timely detection of potential threats, is emphasized. The challenges of AI implementation are considered, including integration issues, the need for skilled professionals, and cybersecurity concerns.

Keywords: artificial intelligence (AI), system monitoring, machine learning (ML), computer vision (CV), predictive analytics, industry.

Introduction

Modern industry is characterized by a high degree of technological complexity, which requires constant monitoring and management to prevent emergencies. With increasing production capacity and increasing technical complexity of systems, traditional security methods are becoming less effective. As a result, the risk of accidents increases, which can lead to significant economic and environmental losses, as well as to a threat to the life and health of employees.

The introduction of systems based on artificial intelligence (AI) technologies opens up new opportunities to improve the reliability of industrial equipment and ensure safe operating conditions. AI allows you to analyze large amounts of data in real time, predict possible equipment failures and identify hidden anomalies that may precede accidents.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the use of AI in monitoring and accident prevention systems at industrial facilities. The paper examines modern AI technologies, their application in various industrial sectors, as well as the advantages and challenges associated with their integration.

The main part. AI technologies used for monitoring

The use of AI technologies in industrial facility monitoring systems significantly expands the possibilities of predicting and preventing emergencies. **Machine learning** (ML) is one of the key tools used to analyze industrial data. ML algorithms are able to learn

from historical data, detect patterns and use them to predict equipment failures.

Supervised learning is a ML method in which models are trained on pre-marked data. This means that the correct output is known for each input value, which allows the model to establish matches. This approach is widely used to predict the condition of equipment and predict possible failures, as the model can use historical data to improve the accuracy of forecasts.

Semi-supervised learning occupies an intermediate position between supervised and unsupervised learning. It uses a small amount of labeled data combined with a large amount of untagged data to train models. This makes it possible to improve the effectiveness of training and reduce the need for a time-consuming data markup process. Semi-supervised learning is especially useful in situations where access to marked-up data is limited, but there is a significant amount of raw data.

Unsupervised learning is also an important method in monitoring systems. It is aimed at analyzing data without preliminary labels, which makes it effective for detecting anomalies. This can be especially useful for identifying hidden patterns and deviations from the normal behavior of the system. The use of clustering algorithms in this method allows you to group data and identify atypical patterns that may indicate potential problems.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of data types used to train models in supervised, semi-supervised, and unsupervised learning.

Figure 1. Types of ML methods depending on the use of marked and unlabeled data

These approaches are actively used to create diagnostic and forecasting systems, which reduces the likelihood of unexpected equipment failures and improves the safety of industrial processes. Supervised learning provides high prediction accuracy through the use of fully labeled data, semi-supervised learning helps to improve models with a limited amount of labeled information, and unsupervised learning effectively identifies hidden patterns and anomalies without the need for pre-labeling of data. All these methods, used together or separately, contribute to the creation of integrated monitoring systems that can adapt to changing conditions and ensure timely identification of potential threats.

Another AI technology used for monitoring is **computer vision (CV)**. It is used for automatic analysis of visual information coming from video surveillance cameras installed at industrial facilities. According to forecasts, in 2024, the CV market will reach \$25,8 billion, and by 2030 – \$46,96 billion. The largest market is the USA: \$6,877 million in 2024 [1].

Object recognition and tracking allows you to control the movement of equipment, materials and employees in high-risk areas, thereby providing an additional level of security. At the same time, specially trained neural networks are able to analyze video streams and photographs to identify defects and deviations in the operation of equipment that can lead to an emergency situation.

Modern CV algorithms use deep convolutional neural networks that provide high accuracy in recognizing objects and analyzing their state. Such systems are used in the oil and gas, chemical and metallurgical industries, where monitoring the condition of equipment and safety is of paramount importance.

Signal processing methods make it possible to analyze vibration, acoustic and temperature data coming from sensors installed on equipment, which contributes to the timely identification of potential problems (table 1).

Table 1.

Signal processing methods [2]		
Method	Description	Application examples
Spectral analysis	Helps to identify signs of instability in the operation of mechanisms.	Used for evaluating vibrations in engines and pumps.
Fourier transform	Used for signal decomposition and identification of anomalous frequency components.	Applied for analyzing acoustic signals in control systems.
Wavelet analysis	Used for analyzing time signals to identify frequency anomalies.	Widely used in seismic data diagnostic systems.

These methods are complemented by predictive analysis, which uses AI algorithms to predict possible failures and equipment failures. Predictive analysis systems are capable of processing both historical fault data and current device operation parameters, creating real-time forecasts regarding the likelihood of problems.

Neural networks (NN) are an important data analysis tool in industrial monitoring systems, as they effectively simulate complex nonlinear relationships between input signals such as vibrations and temperature and output parameters characterizing the condition of equipment. This makes it possible to use the NN to predict malfunctions and detect hidden signs of potential

accidents. In conditions of unpredictable changes in operating parameters, the NN can improve the accuracy of monitoring through adaptation and training on new data.

Special attention in such systems is paid to **recurrent neural networks (RNN)** and their improved versions – **networks with long short-term memory (LSTM)**. These architectures take into account sequential changes in data, which makes them ideal for time series analysis. RNN and LSTM can process data from vibration and temperature sensors and predict equipment deterioration long before failure, allowing timely intervention and minimizing the risk of accidents,

which is especially important for industries with critical processes such as energy and chemical industries.

Modern monitoring systems are increasingly using hybrid approaches that combine various AI technologies to improve reliability. For example, the combination of ML and CV allows you to create systems that simultaneously analyze sensor data and monitor visual changes in the operation of equipment [3].

The use of AI in monitoring and accident prevention systems at industrial facilities has significant potential to improve reliability and safety. The application of ML, CV and signal processing techniques provides in-depth data analysis and informed decision-making in real time. However, the successful implementation of these technologies requires carefully designed algorithms and significant computing resources.

Examples of AI implementation in accident prevention systems

American companies are actively implementing AI-based solutions to improve the safety and reliability of their production processes. In the oil and gas industry, **ExxonMobil** has successfully integrated AI systems for monitoring equipment condition and predictive analysis [4]. Using sophisticated ML algorithms, ExxonMobil analyzes data coming from thousands of sensors installed at facilities. These algorithms make it possible to predict the probability of malfunctions, which makes it possible to carry out maintenance in advance and avoid potential accidents. ExxonMobil was

the first in the industry to introduce autonomous drilling at great depths. The company has developed a patented drilling consulting system that is used in enterprises in Guyana. It uses AI to determine the ideal drilling parameters, provides closed-loop automation that controls the drilling process without human intervention.

The company has launched an Internet of Things (IoT) project that allows collecting all operational data from oil refineries and chemical plants – more than 6 trillion individual data points – into a high-performance computing environment «data lake». This allows us to find new ways to improve the efficiency and reliability of facilities and prevent accidents.

Another example is the introduction of AI by a company in the chemical industry, **Dow Inc.** This corporation uses AI-based systems to monitor chemical reactions and analyze real-time temperature and pressure data. Algorithms based on deep learning are able to recognize the slightest deviations from normal operating conditions and instantly transmit warnings to operators. This reduces the risk of overheating or leakage of hazardous substances. The use of such technologies has led to a reduction in emergency situations and improved responsiveness in detecting deviations.

According to research, the use of technology in industrial and analytical processes covers a wide range of areas. The largest share of applications is in modeling and analytics (fig.2).

Figure 2. Digital technologies used in the chemical industry and planned for future use, data for 2023, % [5]

Dow Polyurethane's (PU) flagship Digitalization Initiative is a comprehensive project aimed at integrating digital technologies to optimize production processes and improve the efficiency of supply chain management. Using modern solutions such as AI, ML and IoT platforms, Dow PU implements analytical tools to monitor the condition of equipment and predict potential malfunctions. This not only improves productivity and reduces the likelihood of accidents, but also reduces operating costs by switching to more predictable maintenance models. The initiative contributes to the creation of more sustainable and reliable production, ensuring more efficient use of resources and improving overall environmental safety.

Another example of the successful application of AI in accident monitoring and prevention systems is **Boeing** in the aerospace industry. This initiative has become especially relevant after two plane crashes involving the 737 Max in 2018 and 2019, which led to significant reputational losses for the company. In response to these tragic events, Boeing has developed a new safety analysis tool based on advanced mathematical models and ML algorithms [6].

The company's safety management system combines data from various internal and external sources, including design and production information, inspection results and repair shop reports. Starting in 2023, the company began using ML algorithms developed in

conjunction with the USA Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) to analyze so-called «Maintenance Difficulty Reports». These documents describe malfunctions and defects in parts that were previously difficult to classify. With the help of a new algorithm, Boeing effectively identifies alarms and prevents potential problems associated with aircraft operation [7]. The safety team monitors 20 key performance indicators that help identify defective parts and other risks affecting safety during the design, construction and operation phases of aircraft.

Advantages and challenges of using AI in monitoring and accident prevention systems at industrial facilities

The use of AI in accident monitoring and prevention systems at industrial facilities provides significant benefits, including increased safety, reduced incident frequency and optimized maintenance processes. However, despite all the positive aspects, the introduction of AI is associated with a number of challenges, including problems of integration, data confidentiality and the need for highly qualified specialists (table 2).

Table 2.

Advantages and challenges of using AI in accident monitoring and prevention systems [8, 9]

Parameter	Advantages	Challenges
Safety improvement	Detection of hidden anomalies and prediction of failures helps reduce the likelihood of accidents.	The need to ensure data accuracy to prevent false alarms.
Maintenance optimization	Forecasting equipment wear and condition facilitates the shift to predictive maintenance.	High costs of development and maintenance of AI systems.
Process efficiency	Reduced equipment downtime through timely problem detection.	Integration of AI with existing monitoring and management systems.
Data processing	Ability to process and analyze large volumes of data with high speed and accuracy.	Ensuring data confidentiality and protection against cyber threats.
Training and adaptation	Automatic learning on new data allows the system to adapt to changing conditions.	Lack of specialists with the necessary skills for setting up and managing AI systems.
Economic benefit	Reduced operational costs through improved maintenance and repair efficiency.	High initial costs for implementation and potential errors during the model training phase.

The use of AI in monitoring and accident prevention systems at industrial facilities opens up wide opportunities to improve the safety, reliability and efficiency of processes. The advantages of such systems are obvious: from detecting hidden anomalies to reducing equipment downtime. However, the implementation of these technologies requires careful preparation, significant resources, and addressing issues related to data security and employee qualifications.

Conclusion

The analysis of the use of AI in monitoring and accident prevention systems at industrial facilities demonstrates a significant improvement in the safety and reliability of production processes. The use of ML and CV technologies makes it possible to detect hidden anomalies and predict potential equipment failures, which significantly reduces the risk of incidents. These systems ensure prompt response to identified problems and minimize equipment downtime, increasing the overall efficiency of the enterprise. Examples of the implementation of AI in practice show a significant reduction in the number of emergencies and an improvement in the stability of processes.

However, despite the obvious advantages, the introduction of AI technologies is accompanied by challenges, such as the need to integrate with existing systems and ensure data confidentiality. Successful use of such solutions requires significant computing resources and qualified specialists to configure and manage systems. Further development of technologies and improvement of algorithms will help overcome existing limitations and contribute to the wider spread of AI in industry.

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